

ECOLOGICAL POLYMERIC RESIDUE BRICK

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ABSTRACT

This integrative project seeks to meet the design needs of civil engineers, the sustainable requirements of recycling. Innovation is a process that comprises the creation, development, use and diffusion of a new product. Thus, the need for alternative technologies with more adequate production conditions is logical, for which it is necessary to incorporate knowledge into existing processes, making them more productive and rational. The problem raised in the project is to study a material engineering with mixtures between polymer and clay in the production of sustainable housing constructions. The general objective is to analyze the sustainability in the use of ecological bricks with a polymer base, specifically, Polyethylene

terephthalate (PET). Specifically, to analyze the technical feasibility of using the produced compost as engineering material; carry out a bibliographic survey of works and reports that present pre-molded or molded in loco construction systems that meet the requirements of agility, quality and sustainability; describe the researched methods showing their advantages, disadvantages, costs and performance and present a case study of the construction method using the polymeric waste brick. The project is justified in the current civil construction market in the new demand as a condition for excellence in the sustainable construction activity. Innovation is a process that comprises the creation, development, use and diffusion of a new product. This work had the relevance of presenting a product that was environmentally sustainable since its production, without large energy expenditure, as highlighted by the ecological brick soil cement found commercially. In order to use the raw material, it was determined that waste should be used precisely, to give it a destination. Therefore, it can be concluded that the construction industry is considered one of the sectors that most cause negative environmental impacts on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, it is of paramount importance to incorporate sustainable, economically viable products that are proven to be resistant to the production . process of construction.

Keywords: Polymer; Precast Building Systems; ecological bricks; Sustainable Housing; Construction.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a lot of debate nowadays around the ecological awareness that emerged based on the fear of raw material scarcity that has been intensifying more and more every day. From the 1990s onwards, movements that questioned the development model adopted by the world since the post-war period began to grow, with this the concept of Sustainability emerged.

The adoption of environmentally sustainable solutions in construction does not always lead to an increase in price, especially when adopted during the design phases of the project. In some cases, they can even reduce costs. Although the price of implementing some sustainable systems entails higher costs, this value should be recovered during the time of use of the building (BERNARDES et al, 2012).

The search for sustainable materials in the construction area has brought several benefits such as differentiated designers, product versatility and added value to the property. In this context, the sustainable brick, also known as ecological, has gained increasing prominence because it is considered ecological and economic, since it is not necessary to perform the firing step, performed in obtaining the conventional clay brick (SIQUEIRA et al, 2016).

This integrative project seeks to meet the design needs of civil engineers, the sustainable requirements of recycling. Innovation is a process that comprises the creation, development, use and diffusion of a new product. Thus, the logic is the need for alternative technologies with more adequate production conditions, for which it is necessary to incorporate knowledge into

existing processes, making them more productive and rational. The (question) problem raised in the project is to study an engineering material with mixtures between polymer and clay in the production of sustainable housing constructions. Based on this information, the use of plastic in civil construction is consolidated as a relevant practice for sustainability, due to the fact that it mitigates the environmental impact generated by the sector by reducing the generation of waste ?

The general objective is to analyze the sustainability in the use of ecological bricks with polymeric base, specifically, Polyethylene terephthalate (PET). Specifically, analyze the technical feasibility of using the compound produced as engineering material; carry out a bibliographic survey of works and reports that present pre-molded or molded construction systems in loco that meet the requirements of agility, quality and sustainability; describe the researched methods showing their advantages, disadvantages, costs and performance and present a case study of the construction method using the polymeric waste brick.

The project is justified in the current civil construction market in the new demand as a condition for excellence in the sustainable construction activity. Innovation is a process that comprises the creation, development, use and diffusion of a new product.

Sustainability is a term used to define human actions and activities that aim to meet the current needs of human beings, without compromising the future of the next generations. In other words, sustainability is directly related to economic and material development without harming the environment, using natural resources intelligently so that they remain in the future. Following these parameters, humanity can guarantee sustainable development (DIAS, 2012).

Environmental issues have become, in recent times, a matter of great concern, and this has contributed greatly to the interest in sustainable practices. According to the National Association of Bioecological Architecture - ANAB, the civil construction sector stands out for the self-consumption of natural resources as well as water, clays and uncertified wood since it is extracted without replacement causing environmental degradation (SANTANA et al 2013).

The project structure is divided into three parts, introduction, development and conclusion, focused on environmentally sustainable (solutions) in civil construction.

The project will assume field research. Since the methodology is based on bibliographic and exploratory research for the realization of this project; seeking to ensure obtaining the most relevant information within the field of study of Civil Engineering and sustainability in construction processes, using the electronic database: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO), texts published by authors in the area, and Google Scholar and Academician.

Deepen exploratory research on platforms available on the internet and field research. Thus, the research is also based on studies of scientific articles, journals and reliable electronic media, and a literature review is also carried out.

2 IMPROVEMENT

2.1 PET Brick - Poly Ethylene Terephthalate

Traditional brick is a ceramic product, made from clay and reddened by baking. The innovation of the polymeric brick, PET, is a thermoplastic polymer that had its first synthesis in 1941, carried out by British chemists Whinfield and Dickson, who continued the work of Wallace Carothers from DuPont (UEHARA, 2013). In Figure 1, the traditional brick is a ceramic product, made of clay and reddened by baking. Generally, cobblestone-shaped, can be solid or perforated

Figure 1 – Traditional solid brick (a) and traditional hollow brick (b)

Source: Construtora Cosmos

PET's excellent physical properties, such as rigidity, toughness, electrical insulation, chemical and dimensional stability, and high melting temperature (260°C) give it remarkable versatility, so that it can be transformed for use in numerous applications. In the form of filaments it can be applied in the textile industry, and in the form of fibers it can be used as reinforcement in civil construction materials, due to its high melting temperature and glass transition value (about 70°C) that allows this material to conserve its mechanical properties at temperatures above 175°C (ISOLDI, 2003).

2.2 PET recycling

Criticisms regarding sustainability in Civil Construction are related to the amount of solid waste and polluting gases generated and the consumption of energy used. Ecologically correct materials can be defined in civil construction as those whose composition does not harm the environment during their use or as elements that can be recycled or reused after use, thus reducing the production of waste.

Knowing that when PET bottles are the one that causes the greatest environmental impacts, whether direct, indirect or post-consumer, because when these materials reach the oceans, seas and rivers, these residues take about 400 years in the degradation process, which can cause to the loss of biodiversity.

PET recycling in Brazil has grown in volume and increased in diversity and quality of recycled products due to the environmental advantages of recycling this waste, such as energy savings, the preservation of non-renewable natural resources used in the production of virgin plastic resin, the reduction in final disposal costs, reduction in the volume of waste generated and consequent increase in the useful life of sanitary landfills, reduction in public health expenses and increase in the generation of employment and income (CURTI, 2007). Figure 2 shows the disposal of PET bottles.

Figure 2 - PET Garbage (Bottles)

Source: Santa Ana, 2020

2.3 Plastic Structure

The use of plastic in civil construction is consolidated as a relevant practice for sustainability, as it mitigates the environmental impact generated by the sector by reducing waste generation. Figure 3, walls built with pressed cement soil bricks have thermal behavior and durability compatible with walls made with ceramic bricks, and can be used both in sealing masonry and structural masonry, as long as they meet the resistances compatible with those required for conventional materials. .

Figure 3 - Clay / Polymeric Brick

Source: Santa Ana, 2020

In addition, when referring to the use of recycled plastic in construction systems, the concept of sustainable construction is strengthened, since the use of polymeric waste reduces the chance of pollution of the environment due to its large accumulation. By allowing the reuse of its properties with recycling, the material can be removed from nature and reused in different ways. In the context of sustainable construction, recycled plastic presents itself as the appropriate raw material for innovative construction systems whose conception is focused on clean, fast and quality construction.

2.3.1 Methodological Analysis

The project will undertake field research, in addition to case studies during the forwarding of works, also with recycling cooperatives to help consolidate the proposed objective of obtaining raw material from plastic materials (PET bottles) and analyze an alternative and sustainable material. for constructive systems used in the execution of plastic modules in the composition of the construction.

The relevance of this work was to develop a product that was environmentally sustainable since its production, without large energy expenditure, as highlighted by the ecological brick soil cement found commercially. In order to use the raw material, it was determined that waste should be used, precisely to give it a destination.

This project is presented on the modular construction process, environmentally sustainable solutions in civil construction. Sustainability is analyzed to demonstrate the use and recovery of waste from the perspective of using resources and ensuring future generations. The work is based on bibliographic research, to carry out this research the review format; seeking to ensure obtaining the most relevant information within the field of study of Civil Engineering and sustainability in construction processes, using the electronic database: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO), texts published by authors in the area, and Google Scholar and Academician.

It presents the feasibility study developed in order to test the use of PET bottle granules for the manufacture of pressed concrete blocks. Geometric characteristics, physical indices and mechanical characteristics were considered, such as thermal conductivity and tensile and compressive strength. recycling to help consolidate the proposed objective of obtaining raw material from plastic materials (PET bottles) and to analyze an alternative and sustainable material for construction systems used in the execution of plastic modules in the construction composition.

The research will be carried out at disposal points in the non-hazardous class II-A and II-B urban solid waste disposal network, for the collection of discarded PET bottles. Regarding the support for the analysis and characterization of samples, laboratories can be used in Campinas, São Carlos, São Paulo, capital and São Leopoldo in Rio Grande do Sul. The target audience of this work is professionals and researchers in the area of Civil Engineering, Architects, especially with regard to studies of the use of sustainability for the most diverse purposes.

The plastic modules will be filled with clay taken from the construction of the lakes. The product of this system seeks to become a rigid structure that adds structural components inside (clay or concrete). The characterization of this composite material will seek to analyze the thermal and mechanical properties.

3 RELEVANCE AND FEASIBILITY

3.1 Process Aimed at the Sustainable Use of Urban Waste for Recycling and Transformation

This Project proposes an Organic-Polymeric recycling solution, with the creation of non-conventional recycling, with waste from Polymers (PLASTICS) and Organic Material. The combination of these wastes can create a new recycling model and with that create a hybrid polymer, which can be used to mold new sustainable and ecologically correct plastic products, since now, the degradation time becomes naturally supported by nature. Figure 4 shows the prevalence of dumps and demonstrates that a large percentage of the garbage generated daily does not receive adequate treatment .

Figure 4 - Landfill - Lagos Region - RJ

Source: Dois Arcos, 2019

3.1.1 Endophytic Fungi

The term endophyte, originally described by De Bary in 1866, refers to any microorganism that lives in plant tissues, as distinguished from surface-dwelling epiphytes.

Different definitions of endophyte are found in the literature, but the one defined by Bacon and Write, widely accepted and used, is that endophytes are microorganisms that colonize the internal tissues of plants without causing

Endophytic fungi are a diverse group of ascomycetes defined by their asymptomatic occurrence in plant tissues. They occur throughout the terrestrial territory, in natural and anthropic communities, colonizing plants in the Arctic, Antarctica, geothermal soils, deserts, oceans, tropical forests, mangroves and coastal forests. In almost all vascular plants, seaweeds, mosses and ferns studied to date, endophytic bacteria and fungi were found. Typically, hundreds of endophyte species can be isolated from a single plant, at least one of which is host-specific. Figure 5 justifies the use of recycled material, which the microorganisms used will be monitoring the parameters that favor their activity, will be inoculated inside the cells of the dump and will start to digest the residues present.

Figure 5 - Generation of Endophytic Fungi

Source: Dois Arcos, 2019

3.1.2 Advantages

- Reduction of 50% to 60% of waste generated in 4 years
- Transformation Recycling.

The urban waste recycling procedure (organic + inorganic material) resulted in a mass with a very significant resistance with homogeneous characteristics, that is, with molding

capacity. This injected mass can be structured in plastic modules usable in civil construction and with a biodegradable characteristic, with a shorter degradation time.

3.2 Sustainable Neighborhood

Today we will be able to build houses for future residents of the self-sufficient neighborhood by applying the product together with the transformation of the city's plastic waste. The key to the future success of a self-sufficient neighborhood is having access to the city's recyclable waste to generate income for residents. I imagined the possibility of the different neighborhoods of the municipality, through a partnership between the collectors and the city hall. Figure 6 presents a model of a house in a future Sustainable Neighborhood.

Figure 6 - Sustainable House

Source: SANTA ANA, 2020

This building style was developed for plastic module use. As the house will not have columns or beams, to support a green roof for native forest, I imagined the use of concrete arches to support this structure.

The plastic modules will be filled with clay removed from the construction of the lakes, so they will also be thermal properties and with the green roofs, the internal temperature of the property will be very pleasant and constant.

3.2.1 Advantages for Sustainability

- Creation of Sustainable Housing;
- Increase in human dignity with an increase in the human development index;
- Employability Qualification of manpower Industrial Attractive

3.2.2 Technical Feasibility of the Material

The feasibility study developed in order to test the use of PET bottle granules for the manufacture of pressed concrete blocks. Geometric characteristics, physical indices and mechanical characteristics such as thermal conductivity and tensile and compressive strength were considered.

The plastic modules will be filled with clay taken from the construction of the lakes. The product of this system seeks to become a rigid structure that adds structural components inside (clay or concrete). The characterization of this composite material will seek to analyze the thermal and mechanical properties. Figure 7 presents plastic modules which can be filled with clay removed from the construction of the lakes, so they will also be thermal properties and with green roofs, the internal temperature of the property will be very pleasant and constant.

Figure 7 - Plastic Module

Source: Santa Ana, 2020

3.3 Prototype

Figure 8 - Bathroom Model Constructed Using Plastic Modules

Source: SANTA ANA, 2020

4 MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1 Materials

Figure 9 – Obtaining a Hybrid Polymeric Mass

Source: Santa Ana, 2020

4.2 Characterization of Materials

- Thermogravimetry (TG/DTG)
- Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)
- Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

4.3 Processing of Composites

The composites were prepared in two stages as shown in the topics

- Stage 1 - Preparation of specimens

Figure 10 – Silicone mold for making the specimens (a) and cylindrical specimens (b).

(a)

(b)

Source: ANA, 2020

- Stage 2 - Preparation of Specimens (prototype)

Figure 11 - Mixing of Materials

Source: <https://segurancatemfuturo.com.br/index.php/2016/08/26/o-impacto-ambiental-das-garrafas-plasticas/>

4.4 Characterization of composites

- Compression Strength Test - ASTM D 695 Standard
- Compressive strength - Standard NBR 8492
- The specimens were removed just before the test and superficially dried with a cloth, respecting the maximum time of 3 minutes until the beginning of the test.
- The dimensions of the work faces were determined with a precision ruler of 1 mm.
- Water Absorption Test - Standard NBR 8492
- Flammability Test - ASTM D 635 Standard

4.5 Tests

The purpose of the test is to prove the efficiency of the new building material. Materials optimization means taking a resource-efficient approach to building design, which results in less material used, and/or less waste produced in the construction process, without compromising design assumptions. While this assessment question is focused on specifying appropriate durability measures, the project team should consider solutions that optimize the use of materials and therefore minimize construction waste (BREAAAM, 2014).

The importance given to the ecological brick test consists of the feasibility of the project and its use in constructions. A widespread alternative as an eco-efficient material that uses earth in its composition is the soil-cement brick, known as ecological brick.

The existence of more sustainable building materials, that is, that at some point their use is justified by the reduction of impacts compared to conventional materials, makes it possible for buildings to become increasingly environmentally correct, added to the adoption of more ecological and efficient constructive solutions.

Building materials can be simple or composite, obtained directly from nature or the result of industrial work. Its correct use largely depends on the strength, durability, cost and finish of the works. The understanding of its properties makes it possible to optimize a series of factors of an enterprise, ranging from its performance to its economic viability.

In addition to the environmental benefit of not having the firing process, the ecological brick is self-locking, that is, it does not need mortar, requiring only glue, reducing the execution time by up to 50%. Its smooth appearance allows the brick to be applied without plaster, further reducing material usage. In addition, it has a compressive strength similar to that of traditional brick, however, the final quality is superior with regular dimensions and flat faces (MOTA et al, 2010; CARDOSO, DETRO, JÚNIOR, 2011).

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Considering that the construction industry is considered one of the sectors that most cause negative environmental impacts on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, it is of paramount importance to incorporate sustainable, economically viable and proven resistant products to the production process of civil construction. .

In view of the preliminary results obtained and their characteristics, from the methodologies used, it is inferred that it is possible to obtain Biodegradable plastic masses from organic and inorganic residues.

The environmental and social issues present in today's society make sustainable development a fundamental concept to think about ways to meet the needs of humanity in the present, without compromising the possibilities of future generations to have their survival needs also satisfied.

In this way, the dimension of sustainability must be present in the various spheres of society, ranging from the preservation of natural resources, through the defense of democracy and the guarantee of human life itself.

Prioritizing social and human development with environmental support capacity, generating producing cities with activities that can be accessed by everyone is a way of valuing space by incorporating natural and social elements.

It was proposed to accompany the production of an alternative, sustainable and resistant material to be used in construction systems used in the execution of plastic modules in the composition of construction in single-family housing of social interest.

In the integrative project, it was possible to develop ecological bricks based on polymeric residues (polyethylene terephthalate) from PET bottle granules, considering the geometric characteristics, physical indices and mechanical characteristics, such as thermal conductivity and resistance to traction and compression. , using different proportions of clay in the mixture with the PET polymer matrix.

In view of what was discussed, it is concluded that the project allowed us to observe new options for technological and environmental innovation in the use of waste and the possibility of creating a sustainable neighborhood using new models in civil construction.

Positive considerations: The period of the project was of great importance, so that we had the chance to learn to live with new technologies and innovations and add knowledge, for the near future we can apply it for a differentiated and quality service.

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Attachments

ANNEX I

Figure 12 - Authorization

Figure 13 - Reference Article

Source: SANTA ANA, 2020

Figure 14 - Reference Article

Source: SANTA ANA, 2020